

The unprudent farmland soil monitoring project

Author's Details:

T. Y. Yeh¹, J. R. Ho², H. T. Tsa²i -

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, National University of Kaohsiung, Taiwan

²Environmental Protection Administration, Soil and Groundwater Remediation Fund, Taiwan

Correspondence to: Prof. T. Y. Yeh-National University of Kaohsiung Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering Kaohsiung 811, Taiwan

Abstract

Soil and groundwater remediation Act was enacted in year 2000. More than ten years has already passed, Monitoring project has been completed, pollution status has been defined, contaminated sites depollution have been launched, a great progress has been made. This paper majorly to depict the extensive farmland soil quality monitoring which is unprecedented in Taiwan and believe has never been done worldwide.

This project was initiated from February 8th, 2002 to August 8th, 2002. The project tasks including digitalization of cadastre, farmland listing, basic information collecting, field investigation, sampling & analysis planning, field sampling, soil sample analysis, data evaluation, suggestion of contaminated farmland control, and analysis of potential pollution sources and transfer routes.

2,251 soil samples, had been sampled from Chang-Hwa County, Yun-Lin County, Nan-Tao County, and Chia-Yi City, and been analyzed in this project. 44% of these samples concentration exceed the soil pollution control standard (Table 1), including 492 farmlands (125.65 ha registered) with total contaminated farming area of 108.38 ha in Chang-Hwa, and 6 farmlands (0.39 ha registered) with total contaminated farming area of 0.39 ha in Nan-Tao County. However, the concentration of samples from Yun-Lin County and Chia-Yi City do not exceed the soil pollution control standard.

To coordinate with the investigation results of the relative project regarding to water and sediment quality of irrigation channels in Chang-Hwa area, the pollution sources are preliminary concluded to be the irrigation channels surrounding the farmlands in Chang-Hwa area. As to the Nan-Tao County, the abandoned brick furnace plants neighboring the farmland are suspected to be the pollution sources.

The results show that the soil of the investigation area in Chang-Hwa County is the most polluted. Based on the Geostatistics study and the distribution of the irrigation channels; the area neighboring the investigated farmland in this project is suspected being polluted. For the farmlands exceeding soil control standard, Geostatistics method is suggested to coordinate with the information

of the irrigation system to clarify the contaminated area so as to be the basis of land control and remediation work. As to the farmlands, not being investigated in this project but with high pollution potential according to the Geostatistics study, detail investigations are suggested. Regarding to soil pollution remediation, it is suggested to coordinate with the effluent control and irrigation channel remediation to achieve an all-out success.

Keywords: soil monitoring, farmland, soil pollution standard

• Introduction

Based on the previous farmland soil small scale monitoring results indicated serious possible heavy metal tainted farmlands was around 1024 hectares. Besides less toxic metal copper and Zinc, the contaminated farmland was around 319 hectares.

This extensive farmland monitoring project has been launched. Specifically, toxic heavy cadmium and mercury have been focused. It intended to scrutinize the serious polluted condition.

Soil and groundwater remediation act has been enacted and executed since year 2000. It has been ten good years till today where lots of remediation techniques progressively employed to improve Taiwan soil and groundwater resource quality. Regulatory agencies, academia, remediation consulting firms, on-site professional engineers all contribute the proud ten years in terms of soil and groundwater clean-up contribution. However, some of technologies were un-environmental friendly even detrimental and damage to Taiwan precious soil and groundwater resources. In Article one of the current Taiwan soil and groundwater Act, it clearly stated that soil is a precious nature resources. Soil definitely is not a waste, shame on us most of current most commonly employed remediation are unlawful and merely aiming to save time and money consideration without any care to our land. Dig-and-dump and soil acid washing are damage employed in almost every single local environment agency soil clean-up project. Lot of money, effort and time has been spent during past ten years. Most of the spending is not improving soil quality.

It is really confusing regarding the lesson learned and gained while used these chemical physical, not environmental friendly treatment techniques. Two remediation approaches, namely dig-and-dump and soil acid washing simply treat soil as garbage, waste, and junk, not the soil law indicated soil is a resource. The purpose of this paper is aimed to raise all your concerns and care toward our precious soil property, toward remediation engineers and particularly those governmental authorities who have so far never taken it as deep thought of current serious situation regarding soil damage.

A novel green remediation approach intends to convey in this paper by employing plant to gradually reduce soil metal contamination through several rounds of planting and harvesting. Unlike phytoextraction, phytoattenuation aims to reduce soil metal pollution in a gradually and less aggressive approach such as chelator assisted remediation (Meers et al., 2010). The initial pollution level generally is lower than most soil contamination sites. Therefore, plant is easier to propagate to increase biomass inducing reliable metal uptake. The conceptual model is shown in Fig. 1.

Attenuation is borrowing from the concept "natural attenuation" which has been commonly proposed as a remediation approach for organic pollutants such as DNAPL (dense non-aqueous liquid) solvent TCE (trichloro ethylene) and PCE (tetra-chloro ethylene) or LNAPL (light non-aqueous liquid) petroleum product BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, and xylene). Natural attenuation mainly used natural pollution mitigation mechanism including microbial degradation, adsorption, volatilization, etc. This approach is targeted to pollutant which is not degraded in a reasonable time using conventional remediation techniques, technical imperfectability, or the cost beyond the affordable monetary amounts, economical imperfectability.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

The constructed wetlands are situated in the University of Kaohsiung campus (22°73'N, 120°28'E). The length, width, average depth and flow velocity were 585m, 5.2m, 0.5m and 67.5m/hr (1.88cm/s) respectively, while the detention pond at point has a depth of 1.2m.

2.2 Water quality analysis

Water parameters, including organic matter (BOD and COD), particulate matter (SS), nutrients (Nitrogen and Phosphorus), chlorophyll A, and pathogenic indicators (*E. coli*) were investigated.

2.3 Microbial PCR analysis

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) extraction and polymerase chain reaction- denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (PCR-DGGE) analysis were analyzed

according to Boon et al. (2001). The Wizard DNA Clean-Up Kit (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin) was used to detect microbial community dynamics in the process of nitrogen transformation in the 1-g sediment samples from surface-flow wetlands. Bacterial 200-bp fragments of 16S rDNA V3 region for subsequent denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE) analysis were obtained with the primer combination of 341 f with a gas chromatography clamp (40-nucleotide GC-rich sequence, 5-CCTACGGGAGGCAGCA G-3) and 534r (5-ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGG-3).

The PCR mixtures contained 10 ng of DNA extract, 4 pmol of each primer, and 5 U of Taq polymerase (Takara, Shiga, Japan) in the final concentration of 2.5 mM of Mg Cl₂ and 0.12 mM of deoxyribonucleoside triphosphates in PCR buffer. The PCR amplification was conducted for 35 cycles: denaturation at 94°C for 1 min, annealing at 55°C for 1 min, and extension at 72°C for 2 min. The equal concentration of each amplified PCR product (2500 ng) was further performed with DGGE using a Bio-Rad DCode system (Bio-Rad, Hercules, California), as described by the manufacturer. The 10% Polyacrylamide gel with a 30 to 60% denaturant gradient was used, and electrophoresis was performed at 60°C and 70 V for 14 h. The gels were then stained with SybrGreen1 and photographed. The relative intensity of amplified bands in the gels was analyzed with Phoret1 ID software (Nonlinear Dynamics, Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom). The PCR-amplified products were electroeluted from gel and then sequenced by provider (MdBio, Taipei, Taiwan).

Those sequences were evaluated using the basic local alignment search tool (BLAST) to determine the closest relatives in the GenBank databases (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). Alignment of nucleotide sequences of PCR-amplified products generated a matrix of similarity coefficients with the neighbor-joining method (Saitou and Nei, 1987). The dendrogram based on the similarity coefficient was plotted with unweighted pair-group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) method for clustering (Felsenstein, 1993).

2.4 Data and Statistical analysis

Data were evaluated relative to the control to understand their statistical variations. A triplicate of water and sediment samples were measured and recorded for statistical analyses. Statistical significance was assessed using a mean comparison test. Differences between treatment concentration means of parameters were determined by Student's t test. One-way ANOVA was also employed to show the variation among sample groups, level of $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant was used in all comparisons. Means are reported mean $\pm$ standard deviation. All statistical

analyses were performed with Microsoft Office EXCEL 2007.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Water parameter analysis

The results of these measurements are shown in Table 1. Algal growth-related water parameters chlorophyll A, COD, turbidity and SS were in increasing order from upstream to detention pond, which induced the fish kill. Serious algal bloom affected water pH and DO due to photosynthesis and the algal respiration effect. Diurnal pH and DO monitoring results are showed in Fig1. Algal photosynthesis produced CO₂ and oxygen inducing pH and DO to rise in the day time. Increased DO was related to oxygen production and pH increase was due to algae using up CO₂, inducing dropping pH. In the night time, algal respiration enhanced CO₂ production to convert generation of carbonic acid leading to pH dropping.

3.2 Water quality and Algal species monitoring

Chlorophyll A concentration for A, B and C were: 192±71.8, 319.7±91.6, 307.2±68.1 µg/L. A, B and C turbidity were: 21.3±6.3, 27.5±6.3, 27.0±11.5 NTU while SS were 17.7±2.5, 30.7±7.8, 34.3±10.4 mg/L. COD concentrations for A, B and C were: 19.1±6.7, 29.1±8.8, 23.0±10.1 mg/L. Total phosphorus concentration for A, B and C were: 192±71.8, 319.7±91.6, 307.2±68.1 µg/L. E coli concentrations for A, B and C were: 28,333 ± 7,505, 8,333 ± 8,082, 2,333±, 2309 CFU/100mL. The main processes for the removal of SS are sedimentation and filtration within systems. Phosphorus removal in wetlands might be induced by the plant uptake, accretion of wetland soils, microbial immobilization, retention by root bed media and precipitation in the water column.

Nitrogenous nutrient transformation in wetlands mainly occurs by biological processes including magnification, nitrification, denitrification, nitrogen fixation and nitrogen assimilation. For secondary treated sewage, the predominant forms of nitrogen might be ammonium and nitrate depending on aeration levels in secondary treatment processes. Nitrification and denitrification are generally indicated as the principal processes for nitrogen reduction (Reed et al. 1995). In this study total nitrogen levels fluctuated from upstream toward detention pond indicated nitrification and denitrification concurrently occurred in the sediment. Macrophytes may remove some nutrients through direct uptake and provide environments for more intense microbial activities. The vegetation in constructed wetlands also creates quiescent conditions for

sedimentation as well as oxidation conditions for organic matter decomposition and nutrient transformation through bacterial activities from microbes suspended in the water column and attached around the root zones.

3.5 .1 Particle size measurement

The result of particle size measurement of three sampling points is shown in Table F. The sediment particle encompassed clay, silt and sand with the particle size in the descending sequence as <2 µm, 2-50 µm and 50-1000 µm. The larger particles of sand were expected to settle more easily than silt and clay. Five sampling points from upstream to detention pond showed that the total volume sand particles were in the decreasing order 74.08, 13.38, 3.1%, respectively, which indicated that most large particles settled in the upper stream sediment. The detention pond presented higher total amounts of clay which possessed higher cation exchange capacity (CEC) and pollutant adsorption in particular metal cation leading to higher metal mobility and bioavailability. This might be the cause that dissolved pollutants having increased and impacted the benthic ecology.

Microbial Identification Analysis. The PCR amplification of 16S rDNA and

DGGE analysis were performed to determine the dominant microorganisms in

nitrogen transformation in the surface-flow wetlands. Figure 3 shows the DGGE

profiles of the PCR-amplified 16S rDNA for sediments collected. The profile of

DGGE for detecting sediment samples showed that six strains of microorganisms

were predominant in nitrogen transformation. The nucleotide sequences of 16S

rDNA variable V3 regions obtained from PCR-amplified products of six specific microorganisms were compared with the database from GeneBank. Nitrosospira

and Nitrosovibrio, the possible species for strain 3, have been reported to

transform nitrogen through nitrification (Chan et al., 2008). Denitrificans, the

possible species for strain 1, and Pseudomonas, the possible species for strain

6, coexisted in the sediment and could have transformed nitrogen

through denitrification. Transformation of nitrogen has not been reported for

some of the microorganisms. If some microbes have similar genetic background

and are closely related to some clusters, the microbes could transform nitrogen

compounds within surface-flow wetlands. Microbial identification results

indicated that nitrification/denitrification concurrently occur within the sediments

of surface-flow wetlands. This result might explain the significant total nitrogen

reduction in the surface-flow wetlands ($p < 0.05$).

4. Conclusion

Fish kill commonly occurs in the detention ponds and surface flow wetland due to algal bloom. Serious diurnal DO and pH were detected due to the photosynthesis and respiration elevating DO and pH in the daytime and decreasing DO and pH at night. Oxygen level fluctuation was the main cause of fish kill in this study site, and the possibility of toxic algae intrusion was left out. SOD and OPR revealed the black box toxic variation levels. Microbial PCR was conducted to illumine the species of microorganism in the sediment. The root of macrophyte was also investigated via SEM, EDX and FTIR. The results of this study can serve as reference for other wetlands or for the future research and solve the emergent fish kill to be substitute of algacide copper sulfate, a toxicant of phytoplankton application.

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Table Captions

Table 1: Water quality analysis results

Table 2: Water quality in detention pond

Table 3: Nutrient content levels in detention pond

Figure Captions

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of pot experiment

Fig. 2: Diurnal water quality variation

Fig. 3: Fish kill events

Fig. 4: Microscopic observation results

Table 1: water quality analysis results

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Temp. (°C)	30.9±2.1	35.2±1.9	35.4±2.6	35.7±2.7	37.4±2.8	33.5±1.7
DO (mg/L)	6.23±2.7	8.48±3.1	17.93±3.9	18.65±3.5	17.15±3.4	14.71±4.2
pH	8.24±1.87	8.48±1.98	8.68±1.95	8.79±1.80	8.65±2.12	8.30±2.04

Table 2: water quality in detention pond

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Chorollphyl A(µg/L)	178.1±68.1	192.6±71.8	336.5±82.1	319.7±91.6	295.4±93.3	307.2±68.2
Turbidity (NTU)	10.0±3.6	21.3±6.3	32.3±7.5	27.5±6.3	25.1±4.9	27.0±11.5
COD (mg/L)	12.8±4.0	19.1±6.7	26.1±10.5	29.1±8.8	24.8±13.8	23.0±10.0
SS (mg/L)	9.7±1.5	17.7±2.5	36.1±1.5	30.7±7.8	28.8±6.4	34.3±10.4
TP (µg/L)	0.176±0.044	0.185±0.037	0.133±0.031	0.149±0.040	0.137±0.034	0.121±0.048

Table 3: Nutrient observation results (mg/L)

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Ammonia nitrogen	4.14±1.73	3.35±1.13	2.23±1.26	1.07±1.07	0.89±0.3	0.70±0.22
TKN	5.36±1.97	5.01±2.27	2.78±1.34	1.61±0.63	0.77±0.62	0.67±0.46
Nitrate nitrogen	1.27±0.57	1.47±0.79	0.87±0.49	1.00±0.42	0.27±0.31	0.31±0.43
Nitrite nitrogen	0.09±0.01	0.32±0.13	0.18±0.1	0.17±0.02	0.07±0.07	0.04±0.03
Total nitrogen	6.72±2.47	6.8±2.26	3.83±1.98	2.78±1.79	1.11±1.68	1.02±0.57

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of pot experiment

Fig. 2: Diurnal water quality variation

Fig. 3: Fish kill events

Fig. 4: Microscopic observation results